

**COVERAGE OF ISSUES OF RAISING THE SPIRITUALITY OF A PERSON IN THE
PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS OF ABU MANSUR MOTORIDI**

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Annotation. This article provides information on the role of the philosophical heritage of Abu Mansur Moturidi in the development of personal spirituality and the scientific analysis of the views of the scholar.

Keywords: Abu Mansur Maturidi, maturidi teachings, philosophical heritage, personal spirituality, religious worldview.

Uzbekistan is a land of great thinkers! In fact, how many great figures our homeland has, a scientist-it is a dwelling that causes fuzalos to conquer the high peaks of science. This land is the land that brought up in the bosom of its beautiful nature, people of sobriety, in general, great figures with their magnificent qualities, which equated to paradise.

Abu Mansur Moturidi, a great scholar, the sultan of the Aqeedah and theology, who was born in the ninth century AD during the Samanid dynasty, also grew up in the ancient land of Samarkand and made a worthy contribution to the development of religious and secular science. It should be noted that the great compatriot Imam Abu Mansur Moturidi and the scholars of the "School of Moturidi", which he founded, have done a great job in instilling in the hearts of millions of Muslims the vital ideas of the blessed religion of Islam. One of the main goals of our research is to study the personality and scientific activity of Abu Mansur Moturidi and to introduce such a great figure to the people. Therefore, the study of the importance of Abu Mansur Moturidi and the ideas of Moturidi doctrine in the formation and development of personal spirituality determines the relevance of the topic.

Raising one's spirituality has always been a topical issue. Because the spiritual image of a society is measured by the level of spiritual maturity of the people who live in it. The process of educating a spiritually mature person imposes a great responsibility on the members of the state and society. In this regard, the establishment of schools in our country, such as hadith, kalam, Islamic law, mysticism, aqeedah, is the basis for the training of qualified personnel who can ensure the compatibility of religious and secular science. Adoption of the Decree PF-5416 "On measures to radically improve the activities of the religious and educational sphere", adopted on April 16, 2018 on the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev, and serves as a legal source for the study of the invaluable heritage of our ancestors, who made a significant contribution to the development of culture, the education of young people as full-fledged people, as well as to ensure a stable socio-spiritual environment in society. Why

does humanity always feel the need for spirituality? What is the role of spirituality in the development of the individual? Is it possible to live without spirituality? Questions like these have encouraged scientists and scholars to work hard in the cause of science and to serve the betterment of human society. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev, in his Address to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 24, 2020, recalled our great ancestors and said: "... we must deeply study the heritage of our enlightened ancestors. The more we study this spiritual treasure, the more we will find the right answers to many of the questions that concern us today. The more we actively promote this priceless wealth, the more our people, especially our youth, will realize the value of today's peaceful life." The great scholar Abu Mansur Moturidi, who risked his life in a very dangerous and dangerous situation in the Middle Ages, set an example of spiritual courage that will serve as an example for future generations. The great honor of being a "corrector" is a testament to the great intelligence and perseverance of this rare person. " In all his works, Abu Mansur Moturidi is far from any manifestation of error, his efforts to promote healthy spiritual thinking in the existing socio-spiritual environment of the people, as well as purely religious and philosophical. with his views he gave sharp denials to the religious fanatics and supporters of the destructive idea of the time. As a result of these efforts, he was awarded the title of "Imam of Guidance" in his time. Although it is known that the scholar has researched about 15 works, we have received 2 famous works of the Sheikh. They are Kitab at-Tawhid and Tawilat al-Qur'an. Through these works, Abu Mansur Moturidi spoke about the philosophical essence of the creation of mankind, the science of monotheism, the influence of being on man, the science of psyche, a certain limit of human power, freedom of will, understanding of the world and the hereafter. based on the verses provided a lot of information. Abu al-Mu'in al-Nasafi, a famous student of the scholar, praised the great character and strong potential of his teacher, saying: "Abu Mansur al-Moturidi was the greatest of the imams and the pillar of the nation. It is a work that reveals, drives the dark clouds of doubt in the human heart, and is created with the utmost character. May Allah bless the one who wrote such a book." Abu Mansur al-Moturidi is an encyclopedic scholar who deserves such a high esteem. and causes an increase in confusion.

The issue of human freedom. Abu Mansur Moturidi, first of all, accepts human behavior as an ontologically clear truth and tries to substantiate this idea. According to him, everyone is the real owner of their actions. It is clear from the verses of the Qur'an that man is the absolute owner of his actions, both mentally and spiritually. Based on this fact, Allah has entrusted people with certain duties and responsibilities within His means. As a result, he was rewarded with punishments and rewards for actions performed or abandoned. In order for a person to perform a certain action and activity, he is given a certain strength and power in practice before the action. Man's actions are the result of this power given to him and the will of the person who urges him to exercise it. This process is the basis of human action and the set of responsibilities placed on it. In this way, a person takes a certain action, chooses and implements it voluntarily.

It is by the power of Allah Almighty to create all the good or bad deeds of man. So, there are two aspects in human behavior: the role of man and the power of God. Abu Mansur al-Moturidi completely rejects the views of those who have accepted the idea of forcing and rejecting the destiny put forward in his case, and emphasizes that deeds belong to both man and Allah. As a solution to this problem, he puts forward a new idea. According to Abu Mansur Moturidi, it is a personal matter for a person to resort to a certain action, to choose it and to do it according to his own will and will. Allah, the Creator of everything, is also the Creator of human action. So, from the point of view of creation, the power to influence action belongs to Allah. In other words, action belongs to man in terms of action, and to God in terms of creation. This partnership in the human psyche is a partnership that has special characteristics and does not eliminate responsibility.

Personal Ethics Analysis. The beauty or ugliness of things, as well as whether they are good or bad, can be understood in general terms. However, the mind cannot identify them in all their aspects and details. He can know after deep research and contemplation, or through the message of a prophet. The statement of the Shari'ah in this regard is a statement and confirmation. The Shari'ah also commands something to be good and makes it unclean because it is bad and harmful. Religion is united with reason in this regard. In addition, the moral sense is inherent in man, and man is by nature a moral being. Because the beauty of some things and the ugliness of some things are clearly manifested in the mind by nature, the mind perceives, analyzes, encourages, or returns to a particular action. For example, the truth of gratitude for the blessings that exist, the beauty of justice, the ugliness of ingratitude, the ugliness of oppression and lying, and so on. Not only does the intellect have the right to act lawfully or unlawfully, which is rewarded or punished in the Hereafter, this authority belongs to Allah. Hence, the science of reason cannot determine the amount of punishment and reward for the Hereafter. Religion promises rewards to those who do what is commanded, and punishes those who are forbidden. Another point to be noted in Abu Mansur al-Moturidi's concept of morality is that he puts idea, belief, and correct knowledge above action, rather than imitation. ra focuses on healthy knowledge.

According to Abu Mansur Moturidi, it is a moral obligation for everyone to know Allah and to know His beautiful qualities. Because the only way to understand being and the knowledge of its creator is through the mind.

Abu Mansur Moturidi has also expressed many views in his works on issues such as making people responsible for their own capabilities. In particular, according to the scholar, in religion, people are never responsible for actions that they are not capable of. The main condition for being responsible for any action in Islam is that what is commanded or forbidden must be to the extent that one can do. Accordingly, the tasks assigned are divided into a set of actions that people can and cannot afford. It is completely contrary to the logic of religion's responsibility to send a person to a prayer or a certain obligation that he cannot perform, and as a result, to punish them for the inadequacy of their actions and for the actions of the subjects of the movement. Allah has opened the doors of opportunity for people to understand what He has commanded them by intellect or

by revelation. It is impossible to refer to a divine command that cannot be understood. There are different ways to know all of these commandments. But it is possible to know the way with the mind and the conclusion.

According to the principle of creation, God did not create any action or situation in vain. According to the laws of eternity, every event, event, and process takes place for a specific reason. According to Moturidi, nothing in the universe was created in vain. Everything has a reason, a purpose, and wisdom. That is why Allah's creations do not go beyond the laws of existence and the foundations of reason. He creates everything in the best possible way and in the strongest way. According to him, there are two types of wisdom: the first is justice and the second is grace. Justice puts everything in its place. And the grace of God is an infinite and never-ending blessing.

"The great source of understanding the greatness of Imam Moturidi and his biography is his works. His devotion, piety, soundness of mind and faith, mental maturity, and intellectual advancement are immediately apparent to anyone who studies his work."

At all times, religion has been a spiritual tool that ensures the spiritual unity of people, the common goal, and the unity of dreams and hopes. This medium has not lost its psychological power over time, no matter how many political conflicts.

"Abu Mansur Moturidi is the pride not only of the fraternal Uzbek people, but also of all Turkic peoples who have made a significant contribution to the development of the Ummah, strengthening the humanistic and rational foundations of the holy Islam." Indeed, the philosophical heritage of the great scholar, the fruit of all his scientific activities and labors, greatly contributes to the improvement of the spiritual image of society and the people living in it today, to spiritual perfection and high philosophical thinking. In today's globalized world, the study of Abu Mansur Moturidi's personality, philosophical heritage and Moturidi teachings is not only our religion, but also the ideological immunity against various ideological threats, fanaticism and radical worldviews that give rise to misconceptions about the whole being, humanity. function. The philosophical legacy of Abu Mansur Moturidi is a very relevant and important source in counteracting and combating the poisoning of the minds of young people with various forms of destructive ideas.

In conclusion, we would like to note that in recent years in our country, special attention has been paid to the study of the lives and activities of great scholars, their spiritual heritage, who made an invaluable contribution to the development of the holy religion of Islam with their profound philosophical views. Due to this, it is important to study the teachings of the great scholar Abu Mansur Moturidi and his main slogan, Moturidi. Indeed, in today's global process, the issue of correct understanding and interpretation of Islam is important. The invaluable role of the doctrine of Moturidism in this regard, the rich scientific and spiritual heritage of the scholar, the development of the state and society, the principles of humanity are widely recognized by a number of foreign and local scholars. Therefore, if we correctly apply the ideas and ideologies put forward in the life, scientific activity and scientific works of this great scholar to the education

system, as well as easily and clearly convey to the minds of our people, we believe that in the future Abu Mansur Moturidi's philosophical heritage We have prepared the ground for its development. After all, the high respect for our great ancestors is the human duty of us generations. Uzbekistan has a great future. It is the sacred duty of each of us to realize that our ancestors also have a worthy contribution to this greatness.

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